

ISSN No: 3433-7018

abstrajournals.com

892 Berne St SE, Atlanta, GA 30316, United States

Abstra International Journal of Management and Business

Volume 13 Issue 3, September 2024

108

INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL MARKETING AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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How to Cite this Paper:

Aniuga Chukwuma
Okonkwo Raphael V. & Okolo
Amaka Nwakaego (2024).
Influence of Digital Marketing
and Artificial Intelligence on
Economic Development in
Nigeria, *International Journal of
Management and Business*, 13(3)
pp.105-121

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14250795>

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Keywords

Influence, Digital Marketing,
Artificial Intelligence,
Economic Development,
Nigeria

Abstract

The objective of this study was to examine how digital marketing and artificial intelligence influence economic development in Nigeria. Two theories guided this study: Marketing Automation Theory and The Schumpeter's Theory of Economic Development. To achieve the objective, the researchers adopted an explanatory research method and it is solely on insights drawn from the analysis of the existing literature of different studies, periodicals and books related to the topic of study. The following areas are where these new innovations have positively influenced economic development in Nigeria. They include: agriculture, construction, banking and finance, marketing, health industry, energy, education, data security, etc. However, as laudable as these innovations might sound, the researchers also discovered in their study that there were some challenges which can hinder the impacts these innovations can offer to economic development of any country. They include but not limited to the following; Data reliability, data uniformity, data volume, privacy, standardisation, regulation issues, marketing and market issues, black boxes, complexity, etc. Therefore, based on the observations made from the literature reviewed, it is recommended that countries that want to grow beyond their current economic development index should adopt these innovations as it have depicted that they are useful in the above mentioned areas and that they should equally work assiduously to improve on the areas that they might be confronted with some challenges.

INTRODUCTION

Every country in the world is looking for better and modern ways of improving and expanding her economy. Many have adopted and embraced innovations as a means of achieving it. Digital marketing and artificial intelligence are some of the ways in which a country can create many avenues for national income, improve a country's competitive advantage and support economic development leading to liveness of the economies (Gontur, Emmanuel & Davirengs, 2018). Today, in order to stay on top of competition and

give maximum satisfaction to customers, marketers need to embrace digital marketing and artificial intelligence as tools and techniques that can offer personalized and relevant experiences to customers seamlessly across every touch point. Digital marketing is the marketing of products and/ or services to customers using digital channels and technologies. It is also referred to as online, internet or web marketing. Digital marketing uses internet as the core medium, though its scope also extends to non-internet channels. Contrary to traditional marketing techniques, digital marketing is more targeted, interactive and measurable. It satisfies the goals or objectives of buyers and sellers, and maintains customer satisfaction and relationship through online services [Imber and Betsy-Ann \(2000\)](#). Recently, many countries and organizations in the world have included digital marketing and artificial intelligence as parts of innovations and strategies to improve their businesses and contribute meaningfully to their economic development.

Artificial intelligence (AI) in other hand, is a new concept that has been taking over the globe in all ramifications, be it medicine, education, entertainment, tourism, construction, business, agriculture or marketing world. We live in a world where information, data collection, analysis and inference are as important as breathing in this world. Every data big or small is stored up and used by businesses. Take a classical example of a user of Instagram. The reels and posts watched by the user on a particular Instagram ID is captured and stored. The next time the user opens his or her Instagram page the posts relevant to what they viewed previously appear at the top. Similarly, if the user has scrolled on a particular promotional post, the AI software captures these data and floods similar promotions on the page.

Today, artificial intelligence presents a better means to expand and increase economic development and opportunities in emerging countries like Nigeria in many ways. It is capable of improving business productivity stemming from automation of core business processes and human capital development and equally can significantly lower production costs. These improvements are already used by many companies in developed markets. AI-enabled productivity growth directly raises output and employment, and does so indirectly through increased consumption. They generate diversified sources of national income, improve a country's competitive advantage and support economic development leading to liveness of the economies.

Artificial intelligence has a vital role to play in digital marketing. AI can help facilitate the creation of new business opportunities [\(Kolbjornsrud, Amico & Thomas, 2016\)](#). It is important that businesses incorporate AI into their marketing strategies if they hope to remain competitive, survive and improve [\(Pradeep, Appel, & Sthanunathan \(2019\)\)](#). This decision was influenced by the prevalence of digital marketing in businesses. Having considered the pervasiveness of artificial intelligence and machine learning and the dynamic nature of the industry, the attention or focus is on analyzing its impacts when applied in digital marketing.

[Kaplan \(2019\)](#) defines Artificial intelligence as a system's capability to accurately understand external input, learn from it, and apply that knowledge to accomplish specific performance targets through adjustable adaptation. Marketing is an area considered to be among the most viable for improvement and it was discovered that the deployment of artificial intelligence in marketing has the most revenue potential and economic development success [\(Fagella, 2019\)](#).

Economic development refers to the total quality of life of a population. It includes the standard of its general living in form of education, medical care and diet. The greater a country's economic development, the better the living standard of people should be. Therefore, it is hoped and believed that when a country or an organization accepts and incorporate innovations like digital marketing and artificial intelligence into their businesses or economy, they intent to achieve more by increasing their production capacity. They also intend to ease way of doing things which can make them maintain or increase their market share, profitability, sales growth, etc. and to give maximum satisfaction to customers and a better future for their economic development tomorrow.

Statement of the Problem

In the era of innovations like digital marketing and AI, some people or organizations are always skeptical in adopting them as means of improving their businesses and the economy of their country at large. Most of them want to remain the way they are to avoid challenges that are usually associated with innovations and not minding numerous advantages it present before them and how it will be beneficial to them. Some individuals and organizations are not always willing to venture into innovation immediately it is launched until they see how others who have ventured into them are doing.

However, it has been proven that there is no country or organization in the world that can exist, expand, survive or compete favorably without involving themselves in new modern technologies. That was why Federal Government of Nigeria having, realized the huge potential these innovations can provide as a new frontier for economic development and social opportunity in Nigeria, went on to establish a Center for Artificial Intelligence and Robotics focused on networking, research development, and information and communication security. Perhaps, this would encourage the rapid adoption of artificial intelligence applications and other innovations across all professions [Nkwede and Aniuga \(2013\)](#).

According to [Mahbub \(1971\)](#), he contended that the problem of economic development must be defined as a selective attack on the worst forms of poverty. Economic development goals must be defined in terms of progressive reduction and eventual elimination of malnutrition, disease, illiteracy, squalor, unemployment, and inequalities, etc. through the adoption of innovations hence this study, influence digital marketing and artificial intelligence on economic development in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to examine the influence of digital marketing and artificial intelligence on economic development in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Concept of Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is a term used to describe advertising campaigns that are displayed on a computer, phone, tablet, or other device. The development and widespread use of technology and Internet technologies have transformed the way society communicates, both in daily and professional life. The same applies to the business of companies operating in modern (digital) conditions. The Internet has become a key component – or, one could say, a strategic weapon in that it represents one of the most significant technologies of the twentieth century [Jithin, Mahalakshmi and Anand \(2022\)](#).

Internet social media and mobile devices have dramatically increased the interactions between firms and consumers through AI, with the information encoded in rich media formats such as text, image, and video. It is imperative for firms to understand consumer perceptions and preferences and obtain brand-positioning insights based on this rich media content (Jabeen, 2022, cited in Ma & Sun, 2020). The ever-increasing amount of consumer data available online, in big data systems or mobile devices, makes AI become an important ally of marketing, as it is based on data analysis in almost every area of its application. Marketing takes advantage of data to a large extent - from consumer needs research, market analyses, customer insights, and competition intelligence through pursuing activities in various communication or distribution channels to measuring the results and effects of the adopted strategies. Marketing becomes a natural beneficiary of developing information technology (Jabeen, 2022).

AI contributes to automating, optimizing, and augmenting three fundamental marketing processes, data collection, insights gathering through data analysis, and customer engagement. Modern marketing builds on intelligence technologies to capture relevant user data from the interactions with the brand. The benefit for the user is better assistance on immediately expressed needs and the anticipation of the unexpressed ones, from a longer-term perspective (Mari, 2019). Traditional marketing practices of promoting host of products through newspaper, radio and television are also taking backstage because of reduced customer attention and giving way to online and digital marketing promotion platforms (Jabeen, 2022) in the like of content marketing, search engine optimization, search engine marketing, social media optimization, social media marketing. Social media marketing channels are only augmenting consumer buying powers as more and more consumers are voicing their opinions about company and brands and related product attributes. Marketer's inability to deliver products in tune with customer requirements can take a toll on company's brand image and values through customer disengagement with said products and brands through online communities and word of mouth (Jabeen, 2022). AI has been making its presence felt quite strongly in the day-to-day digital world of today. With technologies like Chat bots and voice recognition helping businesses offer seamless customer service, it will not be too long for AI to mark the future of digital marketing.

Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology is the processing of human intelligence by various systems and machines such as computers. The basic principle of AI technology is that machine systems perform many tasks, from simple to complex, by imitating and mimicking human intelligence. The goal of AI systems is to reflect the human cognitive system in technology, and thus to transfer the characteristics of human intelligence such as learning, tracking, and logic to machines by using operating systems in various fields. As today's technology evolves, the areas in which the functionality of AI spreads are becoming more evident and advancing. When this system was first used, machines were able to perform simple functions such as calculating, but today, with its use in many areas from advertising to bio-design, the ability to define text or characters or perform calculations has fallen far behind the possibilities. At this point, AI is developing every day and contributing to many industries (Toros, 2023). Artificial intelligence "encompasses multiple technologies including machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), computer vision and natural language processing (NLP)". Artificial intelligence (AI) is "a multi-disciplinary field of research that covers a wide variety of content, technologies and different applications' involving cognitive science, robotics and natural interfaces" (Borana, 2016; Brill, 2018; Nkwede, and Aniuga, C.

(2023). Artificial Intelligence machines and software systems respond to stimuli consistent with human intelligence responses and make human-level expert decisions, helping humans anticipate problems and find possible solutions to problems that may arise (Shubhendu & Vijay, 2013). In this context, it can be said that these systems operate in a conscious, intelligent, and adaptive manner.

Economic Development

Arndt (1981, 1987) demonstrates, the term economic development, as a subject of scholarly work has rather recent origins. The term is closely affiliated with planned investments and intentional development efforts. In his word, people make development occur. Arndt reviewed different opinions about the process of economic development in relation to desired outcomes. Other theories like Neoclassical Theories and models focused on ways to mobilize resources to achieve economic growth and development. Some early scholars considered increases in gross domestic product (GDP) per capita or in income per capita as enough yardstick of good results. Economic development is the increase in the amount of people in a nation's population with sustained growth from a simple, low-income economy to a modern, high-income economy. Its scope includes the process and policies by which a nation improves the economic, political, and social wellbeing of its people. Misra and Puri (2003) define economic development to mean growth plus progressive changes in certain critical variables that determine the well-being of the people. They expressed views that there are qualitative angles in the development process, which may be missing in the development of a given economy expressed in terms of an increase in the national product or the product per capita.

Digital Marketing and Economic Development

Earlier marketers were unwilling regarding acceptable ways of practicing AI in digital marketing but with result of AI in economic development, it has proved that AI will bring dynamic changes in the marketing world, (Shaina, n.d.) in the following areas:

- 1. Generating Content:** Machines can now create content from scratch based on data fed in coding. These can be helpful to save time and resources. AI can write reports and news based on data and information. Automated Journalism is now used by many leading news giants like NTA news, Radio Nigeria, NIPOST and many more. Facebook also uses AI to remove fake news.
- 2. Product Recommendation and Content Creation:** Not just creating content but helping recommending products and services based on the user's search, interest and behavior. Artificial intelligence can rightfully understand the behavior of the targeted audience and what is better than finding the right products or services that you are already looking at.
- 3. Use of AI Chatbots:** There are automated responses used by businesses to solve customer queries and also used in data collection, keeping the audience updated about products and services. They can serve clients 24/7 and retain their data for future use. In addition, the applications of chatbots are huge and the amalgamation of Chatbots with Artificial Intelligence and Machine is the new game changer.
- 4. Web Design:** Without the help of a programmer or a designer, you can still have your website through the use of Grid, that uses Artificial Intelligence to do the work for you based on the information provided like images, text, calls-to-action, etc. they can make the website look professional in much less time and at affordable price.

5. **Predictive Analysis:** Artificial Intelligence uses data to make probable future projections. Predictive analysis is just the use of data, statistical algorithms, and machine learning.
6. **Digital Advertising:** Digital Advertising is widely using Artificial Intelligence to ensure maximum success; it is being used across platforms like Facebook, Google, and Instagram to provide the best possible experience analyzing user information like gender, age, interest, and other aspects to show them relevant ads. With the help of AI technology, marketers can spot micro trends and even predict trends. They can then make strategic decisions as a result; brands can reduce digital advertising waste and ensure that their spending delivers the best possible results.
7. **Online Search engine:** The way of searching content has changed and marketers will need to create and change content accordingly. New innovations include Voice Search and Google's algorithm and other AI advances. Other innovations include Amazon Echo, Apple's Siri, Microsoft's Cortana, and Google Home where they can perform searches just by voice command or pressing a button.
8. **Email Marketing:** Brands are customizing emails to reach their target audience with the power of AI. They can now personalize content based on customer behavior and preferences. Machine learning or automatic learning can now determine the best time and days of the week to contact the user, the recommended frequency through analyzing millions of data. Now they can understand which content catches most attention and which subject and titles get more clicks.

Artificial Intelligence and Economic Development

In our contemporary society, artificial intelligence has been proven to be one of 21st century's innovation catalysts that can impact positively and propel Nigerian economic development performance to another level that can guarantee maximum satisfaction to her people in the following areas of human endeavors:

1. **Energy:** The Nigerian oil and gas industry has been affected by huge costs while undergoing the exploration and production of fossil fuels (Nkwoji, 2021 cited in Mohammed & Shehu, 2023), Due to oil spills, The Nigerian economy experienced a loss of approximately 3,928,260,196 naira in revenue between 1984-2012. This estimation excludes environmental impact, third-party, and remediation costs (Chinonyerem, Ntor-Ue, Chukwudi, & Chinedum (2017 cited in Mohammed & Shehu, 2023). An average of 700 spills are recorded annually causing environmental degradation, while also having a negative economic impact (Ejiba, Onya, & Adams (2016). Mobayo, Aribisala, Yusuf, & Belgore, (2021) carried out a study and found that the major challenges of the energy sector in Nigeria are scarcity of skilled professionals, cellular technologies, outdated power system infrastructure, and the growing threat from cyber-attacks cellular technologies. Therefore, with AI this challenge could be resolved.
2. **Banking and Finance:** It was discovered that most banks in Nigeria utilize chatbots that may enhance engagement with customers. The most frequently used platform for this was WhatsApp. The chatbots were not able to perform as well when out of their predefined path. The chatbots used English and not any of the local languages. Managers know the promise of AI and are open to establishing AI in business banking but note the issues hindering the adoption of AI.
3. **Healthcare Industry:** In the healthcare industry, Nigerian hospital can rely heavily on machine learning to diagnose patients faster and improve the patient registration

process with AI. One of the most prominent Artificial Intelligence software systems actively used in the healthcare industry is called IBM Watson. This technology comprehends natural language and can answer questions posed by reviewing patient information/records and other available data to form hypotheses for patients. As a result, finding and capturing patients' medical information, scheduling appointments and processing payments can be done quickly and accurately. Online virtual health assistants and chatbots are of great importance in predicting, fighting, and interpreting pandemics and are coming to the fore in the health sector as well as in other areas.

- 4. Business and Marketing:** Artificial intelligence is being used continuously and actively in the business world and Nigeria businessmen and marketers can adopt this model in their businesses to fast tract them and to improve on the economic development of the nation and equally give customers maximum satisfaction and profits to the companies. AI is very vital and useful in revealing information on how to improve the service that companies provide to their target audiences or customers. The machine learning algorithms used in this field are adapted to the customer relationship platform and included in the websites, providing fast and instant service to customers with both chatbots and job position automation.
- 5. Education Sector:** Artificial Intelligence is also pertinent in the education sector of Nigeria. Establishing an automatic system for entering grades provides educators and academics with a time-efficient system. Defining students' needs and meeting them in a short time, as well as saving time, provides more support to those in the education sector. On the other hand, professionals working in the field of criminal justice also believe that AI is very important. For instance, AI can be used to screen people who have been arrested for the possibility of offending again in the future, and to store and analyze offenders' records, such as age, offence, activity, and victimization. Forensic experts claim that AI programs will reduce human bias in law enforcement and lead to a fairer sentencing system. R Street Institute fellow Caleb Watney notes that the empirically based questions of predictive risk analysis play to the strengths of machine learning, automated reasoning, and other forms of AI.
- 6. Agriculture:** Agriculture is one of the most vital means of reducing poverty in any country (Omodero, 2021). Omodero (2021) conducted a research and discovered that participation of youths in agriculture as a primary profession could increase the per capita farm income by ₦31,301.22 - ₦32,150.526 and could reduce poverty by 17% (Osabohein, 2021). Osabohein, (2021) discovered that some farmers do not have enough skills to control the pests ruining farm crops and suggested that the government should supply the required facilities such as training, huge markets, modern farming gadget, adequate power supply, and storage spaces to improve agriculture in Nigeria (Omodero, 2021). The cost of farming in Nigeria has increased and this has led to reduced profitability (Osabohein, 2021 cited in Mohammed & Shehu, 2023). They suggested that farmers open tier markets emotionally. The increased cost has an impact on farmers' decision to produce for international markets (Osabohein, 2021). However, with the use of artificial intelligence and digital marketing, famers can comfortable farm, make a bumper harvest and equally market their produce using e-marketing at a reasonable profit.
- 7. Better Housekeep:** The huge demand for home workers around the world is due to the fact that daily life is difficult for many people. As a result, finding and paying for home

employees to supervise their care is becoming extremely difficult. This necessity can soon be replaced by AI because of its current state. In addition, AI can help reduce the level of human trafficking in Nigeria and child abuse occasion by some people who maltreat their housekeepers unnecessarily.

- 8. Data Security:** The common data security challenges make many businesses worry about the lack of ability of their employees to safeguard customer data and other critical data of the business. The cyber-attacks increase is the risk that every e-commerce business has to weigh. Fortunately, AI can help address these challenges by learning, adapting, and reacting to the cyber security a business needs. AI can also be deployed in Nigeria security architecture to improve her operations more effectively and efficient.

Organizations in Nigeria that have Successfully Applied Digital Marketing and AI in their Businesses

The Nigerian business and social strata, has witnessed the application of digital marketing and AI systems to various degrees and the government has also taken steps to harness the advantages of the use and deployment of these innovations. Some examples are found in the use of digital marketing and AI powered customer care systems by institutions cutting across various sectors in Nigeria:

1. Ziva, an AI powered chatbot utilized by Zenith Bank.
2. Timi by Lawpavilion - an AI tool for lawyers.
3. Zigi by MTN - a customer care digital assistant.
4. Lara.ng - an AI powered chatbot that offers individuals conversation-style directions and transport fare estimate while using public transport in Lagos, etc.
5. AI has been deployed in Nigeria for security enhancement, and Chiniki Guard is a company popular in this regard. Chiniki Guard deploys artificial intelligence security solutions for retail stores and supermarkets to monitor, detect and alert shop owners of shoplifting as well as suspicious behavior in real-time.
6. In the health sector, 247Medic, a health ICT application connects doctors with patients across Nigeria within a maximum waiting time of 10 minutes. The application facilitates the provision of auxiliary services, which include lab testing, and doorstep delivery of drugs, to users.

Challenges of Digital Marketing and Artificial Intelligence on Economic Development

The following challenges can affect the operations of digital marketing and artificial intelligence in the following ways:

1. **Data Reliability, Data Uniformity, and Data Volume:** Due to equipment or system failure, data may not be complete and lead to erroneous results. The data may also be noisy or only focused on one aspect. Data could also be collected from multiple sources or may be limited. Combining and finding data may be also difficult (Chen et al., 2015; Sen et al., 2021).
2. **Privacy:** Privacy is also an issue with obtaining health records as patients may not consent for their data to be shared (Ehrenstein, 2019).
3. **Standardization:** Technical and code formats may be stored in various formats such as XML, JSON, etc. (Brewster, Roussaki, Kalatzis, Doolin, & Ellis, 2017). Research needs to

be carried out to promote standardization to increase interoperability among smart systems (Friha, Ferrag, Shu, Maglaras, & Wang, 2021)

4. **Bias and Unfairness in the Algorithm/Data** - if the training data for a model is biased, it may lead to unreliable results. Some records may only contain information from a certain race, gender, or socio-economic factors.
5. **Regulation Issues:** It is vital to set out the legal and regulatory framework governing the management and control of the data and information. (Parasuraman, Anandan, & Anbarasan, 2021). Countries can have different regulations with regard to service facilities such as technological challenges, data protection, and security.
6. **Marketing and Market Issues:** There is a lack of sufficient promotion of smart devices, especially in rural areas. Implementation of smart devices could also be costly (Sinha & Dhanalakshmi, 2022).
7. **Black Boxes:** Consumers may not comprehend the internal functions of AI-based applications (Ahmad et al., 2021).
8. **Complexity:** Some systems may be complex and have high dimensionality of data which could be a challenge in systems (Tang, Huang, Wang, Wang, Guo, & Yao, (2018), etc.

Marketing and AI in Nigeria

In Nigeria, Kafar (2023) cited in Ibrahim, Muhammed and Ahmed, 2023) posited that the news stories about (new innovations and technologies) that are most prevalent are very different from those in the West. According to him, first, there will soon be general elections in Nigeria. While the rest of the world celebrates innovations in Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), the Internet of Things (IoT), and other fields, Nigerians are celebrating the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) and INEC Election Result Viewing Portal (IREV), which some stakeholders have referred to as "innovations." The National Bureau of Statistics data also shows that "63% of persons living within Nigeria (133 million people) are multidimensionally poor." According to Premium Times, "adult illiteracy in Nigeria now stands at 31%." Regarding media habits, AMPS 2020 reports that radio in Nigeria has the highest reach at 81%, followed by terrestrial TV at 75%, out-of-home advertising at 67%, and the internet at 47%. While MTN is deploying a 5G network, Technext notes that "some Africans only have access to 2G and 3G networks" and that "only about 10 to 20%" of Nigerians own smartphones, according to Statista.

Ibrahim et al (2023) asserted that some basic marketing principles, like knowing your target market, will not change. This is because of the fact that some essential parts influencing the operating environment, such as customer demographics, literacy rates, and technology adoption, will continue to have an impact on how companies promote their goods to customers. As a result, not all markets will adopt Artificial Intelligence (AI) in marketing at the same rate. Although it may sound cynical, Nigeria may be one of the countries that lags behind in terms of technological adoption. But if AI is used in marketing, it might take off like wildfire. The mix of marketing communications will still be decided by customer segmentation. According to Anna Holopainen, a B2B SaaS consultant, "Nothing is dead," according to a recent article by Marketing Edge. Advertising dollars are effective. Signs on the street are effective. It's effective to use direct mail. Telesales are successful. Successful inbound marketing. Social selling functions. Campaigns that are drip-fed are effective. SEM is effective. Just determine if it is effective for YOU. The challenging but

enjoyable thing is that. Tiktok started and has Gen Z's attention while some social media users switched from Facebook to Instagram. Yet some people in their 70s are only now joining Facebook. In other words, "nothing is dead."

More so, [Kafar \(2023\)](#) argued that according to analysts, among other reasons, robots lack emotional intelligence, so AI won't be able to completely replace humans. However, ChatGPT provides prompt and, theoretically, remarkable responses to enquiries. In this way, AI will make marketing more efficient and time-saving. As we've already seen, content writers can improve their copywriting by using tools like Grammarly and headline analyzers. Originality and ingenuity will still be advantageous because ChatGPT delivers outcomes based on already available data. Marketers will be able to more easily obtain background data for marketing planning thanks to AI's enhancement of desk research. The fact that all technology is controlled by people means that the adage "garbage in, garbage out" also applies to artificial intelligence. Because of this, marketers can't rely solely on algorithms. In order to analyze research data, human judgment will still be needed. Marketers who immediately utilize AI will succeed, just like the early adopters of social media

Theoretical Framework

This study is accord on these two theories: Marketing Automation Theory and The Schumpeter's Theory of Economic Development.

Marketing Automation Theory

The term 'marketing automation' was first developed by John D.C. Little ([Little, 2001](#)), which he explains as a digital marketing system that assists in making marketing decisions. Little in a Symposium described marketing decisions that can be made by answering certain questions that are critical in marketing. He proposed evaluating a customer's digital footprints and applying relevant algorithms to generate meaningful management consequences for the entire purchase funnel. Through the personalization of marketing activities, such automated marketing decision assistance offers increased productivity, better decision-making, higher returns on marketing spending, and more consumer happiness and loyalty ([Bucklin, Lattin, Ansari, Gupta, Bell, Coupey, Little, Mela, Montgomery and Steckel \(2002\)](#)). Marketers are able to get help in the decisions they make which improves marketing abilities and reduces costs.

Marketing automation was started due to the various issues that the marketing department faced at the time. The aim of the automated marketing strategy was to effectively address customer desires and ensure that customer satisfaction is achieved through technical means. However, there was large information regarding different customer tastes and preferences that was difficult to sort and manage, which would have led to the online system to break down ([Little, 2001](#)). Initially, marketing automation was designed to generically address consumer concerns by providing recommended results rather than the personalized feedback that is done today in terms of pricing, user journey and promotion ([Hinz, Hann, and Spann \(2011\)](#)). Marketing automation has evolved to address personal desires and ensure customers' tastes are being responded to in a particular way

The Schumpeter's Theory of Economic Development

In developing his theory, Schumpeter distinguishes between two types of influences on an economy: first, are the influences of changes in the availability of factors of

production, which he refers to as growth component; second are the influences of technological and social changes, which he characterized as development component. Schumpeter refers to economic growth as “changes in population and in the sum total of savings plus accumulation corrected for the variation in the purchasing power of the monetary unit.

According to Schumpeter, growth component represents the contribution of changes in the utilization of the factors of production. The supply of land being fixed, growth component represents only the contribution of variations in the size of population and of increases in the produced means of production, which Schumpeter distinguishes from capital. Population growth is considered as an external factor in the Schumpeter’s treatment of economic change. Schumpeter believes that the rate at which population changes is determined by factors outside the system. Similar to population growth, increases in producer goods is said to belong to the growth component of economic change. Schumpeter asserts that an increase in the supply of producer goods ordinarily depends on the positive savings flow. The rate of savings in any economy, in turn, rarely rises abruptly. Increases in savings rate are slow and gradual and often require infinitesimal steps. Schumpeter believes that savings are rarely independent factor of change.

Schumpeter looked at profit as an outcome of the economic development process. It gets completely eliminated in the circular flow of economic life, since the value of the output is exactly same as the value of productive factors employed to produce it. Other important factors influencing economic growth and development in Schumpeter’s context include: technological change, entrepreneurship, capital, and credit. Observing such improvements in the field would provide tangible evidence that will allow for a better studying of how digital marketing and AI are influencing economic development.

These two theories therefore were adopted in this study because they are directly applicable within the context of this study since digital marketing and AI are recognized as a rational choice by any country who wants to impact meaningfully to their economic development performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper is a theoretical research and it adopted an explanatory research method and it is solely on insights drawn from the analysis of the existing literature of different studies, periodicals and books related to the topic of study. This research model helped the researchers to examine how digital marketing and artificial intelligence can influence economic development in Nigeria. This study is aimed to service as a way and means of acquiring important information or knowledge regarding the study area. By drawing on the existing literature, not only topic under consideration is theorized, but also formulates and discusses the proposition that will help to illuminate and discuss some key points that are vital and fundamental to assist a country or organization to adopt these innovations and techniques that can lead them to a better economic development performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Every countries of the world desire to develop her economies beyond their current economic of operation by applying some new innovations and techniques. Nigeria and other countries of the world especially the emerging countries have embraced these laudable ideas. To achieve this, some of them have incorporated these modern technologies and innovations into their business activities. Some innovations like digital marketing and

artificial intelligence have been fused into different areas of human endeavor like generating contents, product recommendation and content curation, use of AI Chatbots, web design, predictive analysis, digital advertising, online search engine, email marketing, agriculture, construction, banking and finance, marketing, health industry, better house-help, energy, education, data security, etc. which have assisted them improve beyond their current economic performance. However, as laudable as these ideas might sound, they are without some pocket of challenges that can hinder the impacts of this economic development performance. They include but not limited to the following; Data reliability, data uniformity, data volume, privacy, standardization, regulation issues, marketing and market issues, black boxes, complexity, etc. Therefore, from the observations made from the literature reviewed, it is recommended that countries and organizations that want to grow beyond their current economic development performance should adopt these innovations into their businesses as it have depicted in the previous studies reviewed that they are useful in the above mentioned areas and they should equally work assiduously to improve in some areas that they are confronted or might be confronted with challenges.

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